

THE DEVELOPMENT PROCESS OF AMERICAN LEXICOGRAPHY

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First steps of colonization of Northern America, was reaccepted in XVI c. But they not lead to origin of constant settlement. In the South part of North America (modern state of Virginia) was created the colony of Jamestown in 1606. This colony used the patronage of English crown and her support; in 1619 the ship of Holland brought their slaves – African Negroes. It was the beginning of slave trade in America. The colony of Virginia was the first place in New World where was firmly established the English language; but it did not take place in the process of its establishing [1].

The Mayflower ship moved away from the coast of England in 1620, where were going Englishmen, women and children – who belong to religious direction of puritan; puritans who struggled against abuse and vices of sacred-attendant who called to severity of custom; and it was discussed in persecution by governors of churches. Puritans who moved with Mayflower, was the first detachment of emigrants; in the future emigration of New World became developing and accepted especially large extent after breaking bourgeois revolution in England in the middle of XVII c.

Englishmen: who arrived on Mayflower, stopped on the coast of Eastern-Northern-American continent where they created the colony “New England”. New England was situated in northern part of Virginia and consisted of 6 states on the coast of Atlantic Ocean. The population of the colony become to enlarge; in America were immigrated not only Englishmen, and representatives of other countries and nationalities, particularly Holland and Germans. Many colonists of the ground searched new soil and pointed at the West, fights with time – honored settlers - Indian tribes accompanied this advancement. The chances were unequal, so the colonists had the firearms. Long standing Advancement to the West finished when American colonists occupied whole the territory of Modern United States. The USA declared itself as an independent State; the fighting for the independent was finished with defeating of England. From the end of XVIII to the middle of XIX c. continued the second World wave of immigration; in the structure of immigrants were the main Ireland and Germany; Again at the end of XIX c. came alive immigration of Englishmen and German. At the beginning of XX c. among immigrants were many of Italian and the representatives of West Slovene nationality.

These different waves of immigration left clear track in heterogeneous structure of lecture of American variant.

In XIX c. appeared the work of the language of USA. In 1816 published the dictionary of John Pickering under the title “A Vocabulary, or Collection of Words and Phrases which have been supposed to be Peculiar to the United States of America” [2, 14].

This was the first work in which were collected Americanism. At the same time the position of J. Pickering was about Briticism; J. Pickering tried withdrawing the treatment from the circulation which coincided with British norm. Against Pickering came Noah Webster who protected the rights of Americans in his own scientific work.

In 1828 Webster published his famous dictionary “An American Dictionary of the English language”. This dictionary was compiled fully in vocabulary, forms and pronunciation, the characteristic to the English language of USA, and had a large meaning for the establishment of the American written norm. It often reprinted with correcting and changes and the last edition was in 1901. It was one of the biggest modern dictionaries of the English Language. Webster was a supporter making easier the orthography, in such position it had a big place in the future correctness of several written types, which were accepted in USA. It was the cause of a lot of wranglers and question, is the language of USA considered as an independent language and we may say about the being of American language. It’s known that the English language of the USA did not disperse so, that each of them speaking Englishmen could not understand themselves; knowing one of these variants easily read any text, which was written in the other hand. These facts say that negatives about noticing the language of the USA as a special “American Language” [3, 129].

On the other hand, the language of the USA is the state’s language of independent country, the language of American nation; therefore it presents perfectly unfounded existing till recent time and the conservative view of the English circle to the language of USA as “broken” dialect of the English language.

In this question took place highly extreme position H.L. Menken. In his book “the American Language” which was published in 1938. That this author had required the language of USA is especial English language. Having nothing common with English, just the origin. Menken tries to make a principle in the norm using the simples of form (I seen him) and etc. the other modern linguists, writing about the language of USA, takes place large position.

There are many different ways to approach the problems of meaning, since meaning is related to many different functions of language. The meanings of words in a language are interrelated and they are defined in part by their relations with other words in the language.

Analyzed in the same semantic domain, words can be classified according to shared and differentiating features. Breaking down the sense of a word into its minimal distinctive features, componential analysis of meaning can be a useful approach in the study of meaning, particularly in determining the meaning of a lexeme. Although componential analysis has some difficulties and limitations in its application, it is still used in modern linguistics.

Finegan [4] distinguishes three types of meaning, i.e. linguistic, social, and affective meaning. Linguistic meaning encompasses both sense and reference. One way of defining meaning is to say that the meaning of a word or sentence is the actual person, object, abstract notion, event, or state to which the word or sentence makes reference. Referential meaning may be the easiest kind to recognize, but it is not sufficient to explain how some expressions mean what they mean.

For one thing, not all expressions have referents. Social meaning is what we rely on when we identify certain social characteristics of speakers and situations from the character of the language used. Affective meaning is the emotional connotation that is attached to words and utterances.

A word or lexeme presents a complex semantic structure. A lexeme is built up of smaller components of meaning which are combined differently to form a different lexeme. The meaning of a lexeme is a complicated structure where elements of meaning have definite interrelation [5].

All semantic elements in a word are not equally important. One (or some) of them is the dominant semantic element and it organizes around itself all the other ones, which may be more or less important for the meaning of a lexeme [3].

A lexeme can be analyzed and described in terms of its semantic components, which help to define different lexical relations, grammatical and syntactic processes. The semantic structure of a lexeme is treated as a system of meanings. To some extent we can define a lexeme by telling what set it belongs to and how it differs from other members of the same set. Some obvious sets of this sort are sports (*tennis, badminton, soccer, golf, basketball,...*), colors (*red, blue, yellow, green, pink, ...*) and creative writing (*novel, poem, short story, essay, biography,...*). It is not difficult to say what the members of each set have in common.

According to Semantic field (or semantic domain) theory, lexemes can be classified according to shared and differentiating features. Here are more examples. Wasp, hornet, bee and other items denote ‘flying, stinging insects’; moth and housefly, among others, denote insects that fly but do not sting; ant and termite are names of insects neither fly nor sting. The semantic features explain how the members of the set are related to one another and can be used to differentiate them from one another. The determination of such features has been called componential analysis [6].

This writing treats only the componential analysis of referential meaning.

Palmer [7] says that the total meaning of a word can be seen in terms of a number of distinct elements or components of meaning. Components have a distinguishing function and serve to distinguish the meaning of a lexeme from that of semantically related lexemes, or more accurately they serve to distinguish among the meanings of lexemes in the same semantic domain. To determine the meaning of any form contrast must be found, for there is no meaning apart from significant differences. Nida states “If all the universe were blue, there would be no blueness, since there would be nothing to contrast with blue. The same is true for the meanings of words. They have meaning only in terms of systematic contrasts with other words which share certain features with them but contrast with them in respect to other features”. Jackson in “Words and their meaning” and Nida in “Componential Analysis of Meaning” [8] categorize the types of components into two main types, i.e. common component and diagnostic or distinctive component.

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